

Factors leading to widespread of corruption in government institutions in Khartoum – Sudan

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Abstract:

The most paramount issue that has become concerning to scholars, observers, researchers, writers, international organizations like Transparency International and medias is the matter of corruption, therefore this paper discussed the factors that lead to widespread of corruption in Khartoum- Sudan-. the approach of this paper is descriptive and qualitative method. In order to collect data and information the researcher used secondary data sources such as: books, references, articles, newspapers, internet and reports in addition to other documents that related to the subject. To analyse the data, the investigator used NVivo 12 Plus, using crosstab, matrix and cluster analysis. The feedback of this paper is examining of four main factors that lead to widespread corruption in Khartoum- Sudan namely: Absences of the rule of law, weakness of Judiciary, Lack of political opposition and weakness of civil society organizations. In order to curb the corruption in Khartoum -Sudan- the rule of law must activate, Judiciary must be independent, freedom for civil society organizations to create bodies that observe the act of the government and liberty to the political oppositions to play their role.

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1. introduction:

Corruption is an international phenomenon that spreads around the world, many countries whether in Europe, Asia, Australia, North America, South America or Africa suffering from the corruption but different grades, some countries high others low. The high levels of corruption always being obtained by the countries where there is less democracy, less transparency, less education. Africa is the continent where the corruption is in very high degree, a report of Transparency International says; among four people in Africa one of them payed bribe for accessing service.it refers to that the main reasons of corruption are no doubt exist enough in Africa such as low income, wars and conflicts, no press freedom and no real democracy. (Transparency International, 2018)

Sudan is not exception of the world, in addition to that, it locates in African continent where there is very high level of corruption. Sudan gained it's independent from Britain since 1956, after the independent Sudan witnessed many troubles such as civil wars in (south, east and west), financial crisis (*Corruption and anti-corruption in Sudan 1 Overview of corruption in Sudan*, 2012) . in 1989 there was military coup in Khartoum, it was leaded by Omer AL basher against the prime minister Al Sadig Almhdi, during his rule since 1989 to 2019 Sudan witnessed different forms of corruption whether in Khartoum or in other states. according to the Transparency International Sudan is the sixth most corrupt country out of 180 countries that were surveyed around the world .In Sudan, corruption can be exist in all public institutions of economic and in at different levels of the state, it found in various shapes political , financial , nepotism, embezzlement and in addition to grand and petty corruption (*Corruption and anti-corruption in Sudan 1 Overview of corruption in Sudan*, 2012).thus, we can declare that corruption is problem and indeed in need of solution. The tools of solution can be civil society participation in formation and building of democracy, press freedom will be as an anti-corruption tool and real democracy(Dimant & Tosato, 2017). The questions that arise are:

- i. what are the main factors beyond the corruption in Khartoum-Sudan?
- ii. How to curb the corruption in Khartoum- Sudan?

2. Literature review:

2.1 The concept of corruption:

The word corruption comes from the latin word (corruptus) that means corrupted(Drahansky et al., 2016). and in general form, corruption defined in several formulations and contexts as a result of that the writers and researchers have various backgrounds. one of the researchers defined it as : the misuse of a trusted position in one of the branches of the power with the intention of gaining tangible benefit that is not legally allowed for others to do the same(Drahansky et al., 2016). Another writer defined corruption as: the use of public resources for self-interests. Also it defined as the misuse of power for private benefits via fraud, extortion, bribery and nepotism. (Elamin, 2019). Elamin in his article discussed the elements that considered as the reasons beyond the depravity such as weakness of judiciary system, low wages of public servants, absence of transparency and the absence of the rule of the law. despite corruption is unlike from state to state, it is possible to discover the most common elements that create the depravity in the worldwide(Drahansky et al., 2016), such as: the deterioration of the economic; he clarified that when the economic situation is bad in a particular country , the corruption appears, also corruption is related to the standard of education, when there is high level of education , there is low level of corruption.

Corruption is widespread where the institutions are weak or less democracy, and many democratic institutions around the world are threatened by dictator leaders. Moreover corruption is increase where the democratic foundations are weak and are captured by the populist politicians, using them to their advantage(Transparency International, 2018).the freedom of economic which means freedom of choosing what to produce, what to sell and what to use in your own resources may decrease the levels of corruption in country or agencies.(Dimant & Tosato, 2017). Diman and Tosato in their article which was on (causes and effects of corruption: what has past decade's empirical research taught us?) found that there is a relation between corruption and bureaucracy, freedom of press, freedom of economy, poverty and wages, in addition to the correlation of corruption with the political

competition, foreign direct investment and inequality of income. The system of judiciary also play role in increasing or decreasing the level of corruption in Sudan, when the judiciary is independent, the law should be applied completely, and it lead to decreasing of forms of depravity like: embezzlement, fraud, bribe and discrimination between citizens regardless what class he is or what group he belongs to, or what is his religion or where he come from. the Sudanese constitution declared the separation of three authorities namely; executive authority , legislative authority and judiciary authority , but on the ground it is different, because the higher courts are always subject to the political domination, furthermore the executive power prevails the judiciary authority because the executive power has the right of appointing of judges and the right of dismissing judges (Answer, 2017).

As a result of deterioration of economic, widespread of corruption and dictatorship, the peaceful revolution took place in in Sudan against the rule of Albasher, it started in 11th of December 2018 and continued until the collapse of his rule 11th of April 2019. Abdul Fatah Al Burhan came as the president of sovereign transitional council. In his addressing in Shandi – Sudan – Burhan promised the people that they will bring peace , combat the corruption and nepotism in Sudan .(Sudanjem.com, 2019). Another study found that Sudanese press should work to promote the realization among the journalists and citizens toward the significant of knowing the law of accessing the information, press freedom raises the awareness between the civilians and all the people, therefore it leads to transparency and fighting the corruption in the country.(Bashir, Mohammed, & Khirie, 2018). Study in Nigeria was examined that E-government is a good tool to reduce the corruption in the countries and institutions(MácHová, Volejníková, & Lněnička, 2018), furthermore , using ICTs will minimize the levels of corruption, but to be effective the government needs to make training for his staff and implementation of e-government in local and national levels(MácHová et al., 2018). A research refer to that open government has reacting effect on decreasing the corruption depending on the rule of law which consider as a moderator between corruption and unlock government (Relly,2012).the feedback of his study, was the empirical evidence that the adoption of E-government has impact on the reducing of corruption in its several forms whether it was administrative or financial(Park & Kim, 2019). Many studies refer that the

implementation of E-government in different levels of government – national, local – should curb the widespread of corruption in its various shapes bribery, embezzlement , fraud , extortion and nepotism.(Park, 2018).

2.2. Factors that lead to widespread of corruption in Khartoum- Sudan.

figure1: the factors that motivate spoilers to corrupt.

2.2.1. Absence of rule of law:

Rule of law is the system of governing that prevails institutions, laws and society commitment which delivers four(4) international principles namely; open government, accountability, justice and just laws(Project, 2019). Sudan was colonized by Britain and obtained its independent in 1956 , since the independent until 2019 ,Sudan was not able to create the constant constitution, and governing system that warranty the rule of the law which guarantee the above principles (Answer, 2017).in Sudan the law has been considered as the tool to serve the interests of those whom in the authority, and there is no respect for the constitutions, although the constitutions are the most important tool to manage the country, and this refers to the absence of rule of law (Lutz Oette and Mohammed Abdel-Salam, 2014). Corruption has many faces in Sudan and it is difficult to arrest those whom corrupt because they are protected by authority its self, therefor, the formal Director of Criminal Investigation

Major General Abdul Ghani Khalafallah said; for enormous corruption, the mantle of law procedures does not widen (Shanker, 2019). The law of no-man's wealth gives right to citizens to report about any one of officials who subjected to no-man's wealth, and it will guarantee the accountability of previous regime members whom corrupted (Hamadnaallah, 2019).

2.2.2. Lack of political opposition:

The political opposition consider as the important tool that used against corrupts in regimes. Political opposition can drive out the corrupt officials in their offices particularly during the electoral process. But, because there is weakness of political opposition in Sudan the previous regime which was leaded by Omer Albasher dominated the political parties via his decrees. In 2015 the regime issued a decree, prohibiting the oppositions to organize any kind of meetings in their own venues without the permission of the government, the head of oppositions and activists are arrested without any charge (Answer, 2017). The political opposition in Sudan are divided into three: those whom carry weapons, peaceful political oppositions and opposition whom use both weapons and politics. (Abulfudol, 2018). The previous regime succeeded in weakening the political oppositions whether by wealth or favouritism and splitting them, (Abdulgader, 2019). Furthermore, another writer says; there is no real political opposition in Sudan. The Sudanese political opposition is a big name that has strong echo, but if you look on the ground, there you can find nothing, the oppositions are so weak, their weakness return back to many factors such as: the absence of internal dialogue, the inability to renew the political discourse to fit the internal and external changes, the absence of convincing and practical alternative program and pervasive types of corruption and lack of transparency in its administration (Gada, n.d.).

2.2.3. The weakness of civil society institutions:

The start point of civil society in Sudan return back to the early years of the 20th century, represented by the forms of religion groups, semi-trade unions, societies and academic associations, which resisted the colonial rule, the main association in that period was the (white flag society) that was resisting the colonial regime. The civil society organizations were enabled to topple two dictator regimes namely: Aboud regime in October 1964 and Numiri regime in April 1985. But in the Period of Omer Albasher regime the old civil societies

organizations were dissolved, in that era it was difficult to draw clear line between political parties and civil societies, this is because government use them for her own purposes(Assal, 2016). Although the temporary national constitution and law gives the right for creating associations and unions, but the government – previous – has restricted this right, therefore the space of the civil society has narrowed by the regime, government locked numbers of civil society organization and refused to register them.(Answer, 2017). Civil societies play very high role in change of situations, but the government of Sudan increased pressure against the civil society in 2013 and went on then. during protesting in September 2013 many peaceful demonstrators were killed in the streets of Khartoum and other cities, one year after this clash the govern declared campaign on civil societies organizations and that included detaining a round 48 activists. again in 2015 government launched crackdown on the CSOs , including human rights defenders, Students, media, and numbers of political opposition and denied the CSOs to observe the elections(ICNL, 2019).

2.2.4. The weakness of judiciary:

In Sudan, in the era of national congress party 1989-2019, the judiciary was not independent, there is political interferences, higher courts are subjected to political control, judiciary was suffering from poor infrastructures, lack of resources, in-adequate training, long trial postpones and low salaries. The president was appointing all the judges of courts including Supreme court, on the recommendation of National Judiciary commission NJC, but it was also subjected to government pressure , therefor transparency and independence could be questioned in condition of practice(*Corruption and anti-corruption in Sudan 1 Overview of corruption in Sudan*, 2012). The non-attendance of laws and regulations that interest in the issues of corruption and spoilers strengthen the widespread of corruption, in Sudan rarely the spoilers are caught because of corruption, and when there is crime and no punishment, then it will increase, therefore the non-attendance of law create and maximize the corruption. As above mention that the judges suffering from the low wages and not they are alone, but others also, A study show as the relation between corruption and law salaries , it says; low wages always invite corruption and also it is not sure that officers with higher wages will not commit corruption(Elamin, 2019). In Sudan, officials that suspected of corruption usually not

asked and go without punishment. Corruption in the shape of passive bribery and active bribery of public servants is covered by the criminal code of Sudan, moreover, other forms of corruption include; embezzlement, criminal breach of trust and extortion in addition to other wrongdoing that represented in isolating of public properties (Https://www.ganintegrity.com/portal/country-profiles/sudan/, 2019).

3. Methodology of research:

This study uses the descriptive and qualitative approach, which portray the phenomena of corruption and the factors that lead to widespread of corruption in Khartoum -Sudan. To analyse the factors that causes the depravity phenomena, the writer uses Software NVivo12 Plus. In order to collect the data and information, the investigator uses secondary data sources as: journals, books, newspapers, annual reports of Sudan government, websites and additional subjects that relevant to the topic. In NVivo12 Plus analysis the investigator uses Crosstab query, Matrix Coding query and cluster analysis features, cluster analysis is used to shows the variation and likeness of data.

4. Results & Discussion

4.1. Findings:

The following are the results that gotten by using NVivi12plus.

	Absence of rule of law	Lack of political oppositions	Weakness of civil society organizations	Weakness of Judiciary	Total
Albayan newspaper	20.51%	9.09%	4.69%	21.59%	15.33%
GAN report	8.97%	13.64%	9.38%	9.09%	9.85%
globallex	16.67%	11.36%	14.06%	15.91%	14.96%
Middle east newspaper	17.95%	13.64%	10.94%	12.5%	13.87%
Radio dabanga	5.13%	13.64%	6.25%	4.55%	6.57%
Rule of law initiative	2.56%	2.27%	1.56%	2.27%	2.19%
Sudanese online	2.56%	11.36%	3.13%	5.68%	5.11%
Sudanile	5.13%	9.09%	28.13%	5.68%	11.31%
The Guardian	7.69%	11.36%	9.38%	10.23%	9.49%
Transparent International	7.69%	4.55%	6.25%	7.95%	6.93%
United states institution of ...	5.13%	0%	6.25%	4.55%	4.38%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Figure1: The above table shows the result of NVivo12plus analysis of cases and nodes.

Cases are the materials or sources that the researcher got data and information in, whereas Nodes are the Factors that lead to widespread corruption, which the investigator gained them from the literature review.

Absence of the rule of law:

Albayan newspaper shows that 20.51% of the factors that lead to the widespread of corruption in Khartoum Sudan is the absence of the rule of law, GAN report shows 8.97% , Globalex refers 16.87 , middle east newspaper clarifies 17.95, Radio Dabanga displays 5.13%. Rule of law initiative offer 2.56%, Sudanese online shows 2.56, Sudanile 5.13%, the Guardian displays 7.69%, transparency international tell shows 7.69%, United states institution of law displays 5.13%.

Lack of political opposition:

The cases show us different rates for the lack of political opposition as one of the factors that lead to corruption in Khartoum -Sudan, they are as following: Al bayan shows 9.09%, GAN report represent 13.64%, Glabalex displays 11.36%, Middle east newspaper offer 13.64%, Radio Dabanga shows 13.64%, Rule of law initiative shows 2.27%, Sudanese online shows 11.36% , Sudanile show 9.09%, The Guardian displays 11.36%, Transparency international show 4.55%, and United states institution of law shows nothing.

Weakness of civil society organizations:

Weakness of civil society organizations as a factor that leads to corruption in Khartoum-Sudan is also shown its rates as following:

Al bayan newspaper shows 4.69% , GAN report displays 9.38%, Globalex shows 14.06%, Middle east newspaper offer 10.94%, Radio Dabanga shows 6.25%, Rule of law initiative refers to 1.56%, Sudanese online pointed to 3.13%, Sudanile shows 28.13%, The Guardian displays 9.38%. Transparency international offer 6.25%, United states institution of law shows 6.25%.

Weakness of Judiciary:

One of the most significant factors that lead to corruption in Khartoum -Sudan is the weakness of Judiciary, it is shown in various estimations, as following:

Al bayan newspaper shows 21.59%, GAN report shows 9.09%, Globalex offer 15.91%, Middle east newspaper displays 12.5%, Radio Dabanga represent 4.55%, Rule of law initiative shows 2.27%, Sudanese online refer to 5.68%, Sudanile displays 5.68%, The guardian Shows 10.23% and United states institution of law shows 4.55%.

4.2. Discussion:

Absence of the rule of law:

Figure2: the result of crosstab analysis.

All the cases refer that, the absence of rule of law play an important role in widespread of corruption in Khartoum- Sudan, absence of the rule of law and regulations that control the corruption and doers of it strengthen the widespread of depravity in its various forms such as embezzlement, fraud, extortion, bribery, nepotism, patronage and speed payment. as Babiker (2014) mentioned that the rule of law means: all the people, entities and institutions, private and public, including the country itself are accountable in front of the rule of the state, it requires the application of the commitment to supremacy of the law, transparency and the fairness in the implementation of the law, disconnection of the authorities – executive, legislative, judiciary- and engagement in decision-making, in addition to the independence of the judiciary. In Sudan case, law has been used as a tool to carry out the interests of the

power. Lack of constitutionalism is also point of the absence of the rule of law, Sudan had many constitutions but not respected.(Lutz Oette and Mohammed Abdel-Salam, 2014). The occupation of law in Sudan had suffered a lot from the outcomes of the deep modifications which implemented in the period of (Ingas) ruling, that was included; group dismissal of judges, alteration in curricula, expatriation of big number of advocates, change in medium of instruction and reducing of the criteria. Also, the writer showed that, many of Sudanese laws are conflicting with the Code and the global criterions; specifically, international human rights law. Add to what said; law was – In Ingas era- used as a device for political or ideological objectives and as a facility of control and suppression.(Lutz Oette and Mohammed Abdel-Salam, 2014).

Weakness of Judiciary, weakness of civil society and lack of political oppositions:

Figure3: Result of Matrix coding query.

The above result, explains the most significant factors that leads to widespread of corruption in Khartoum- Sudan namely; absence of the rule of law, weakness of judiciary and weakness of civil society organizations, whereas lack of political oppositions play low role in corruption widespread. As Neimatallah Elamin(2018) mentioned that the judiciary in Sudan is not freelance and more often subjected to the political interference, a lot of objections and complains have raised, pointing to the committing of corruption by high level of politicians

and public civil servants but, there was no comment by the judiciary although it was raised to them, therefore it emphasise the non-independent of judiciary (Elamin, 2019). Furthermore, judiciary in Sudan – in the era of NCP- was controlled by power of executive, the process of recruitment in courts was determined by the admission to regime sometimes by the nepotism. The main challenge for the foreign investors in the courts was the inefficiency of the judges because they are less trained and have no experiences. For instance, judges in Darfur Region were often being absent, postponing the judgements and the judicial agencies are less accessible in countryside areas (Messick, Mulukutla, & Hoppe, 2015). Also, the figure refers that the weakness of civil society organizations perform a humble function in the widespread of depravity in Khartoum- Sudan, civil society is known as: a big set of brotherhoods: including non-governmental organizations , community groups, indigenous groups, labour unions, charitable organizations , occupational brotherhoods, faith-based organizations and institutions.(Jezard, 2018).the constitution and law of Sudan allow people create associations, unions and any form of gathering persons, but the government has severally trapped this prerogative and as the consequence of that the civil society organizations's space became narrow. A student peaceful demonstrations movements were prohibited in many cases. (Messick et al., 2015). Furthermore, the figure shows us that the lack of political opposition plays less function in the widespread of corruption in Khartoum - Sudan, because the rule of law, strong judiciary and powerful civil society organizations will stop or reduce the corruption in its various shapes. To curb the corruption, ruling must be rule of law, independent judiciary, freedom and democracy.

5. Conclusion:

This article has discussed the most important factors that lead to widespread of corruption in Khartoum- Sudan, these factors are: Absence of the rule of law, weakness of Judiciary, lack of political oppositions and weakness of civil society organizations , according to the analysis of NVivo12plus, the researcher found that the most paramount factor that causes the corruption in Khartoum -Sudan is the Absence of the rule of law, the second element is the weakness of Judiciary in addition to the weakness of civil society organizations and lack of political

oppositions. To access the result, the investigator used several sources to compile the data and information such as, NVivi12plus, journals, references, newspaper, internet and books.

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